

Received 9 February 2025; revised 13 March 2025; accepted 21 March 2025. Date of publication 31 March 2025; date of current version 12 August 2025.

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/OJAP.2025.3556282

Analysis and Experimental Characterization of a Uniplanar Metamaterial-Inspired Substrate Integrated Waveguide for Easy-to-Implement mmWave Components

MARIA-THALEIA PASSIA^{1,2} AND TRAIANOS V. YIOULTSIS¹ (Member, IEEE)

¹School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, 54124 Thessaloniki, Greece

²Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Duke University, Durham, NC 27708, USA

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: M.-T. PASSIA (e-mail: passiamg@ece.auth.gr).

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement 101146306.

ABSTRACT We fully explore the properties of a novel uniplanar metamaterial-inspired substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) for realizing easy-to-fabricate mmWave components. Conventional SIWs have a complex fabrication process, especially for higher frequencies, due to the need for drilling holes and injecting metallization. We substitute the vias of the conventional SIW with grounded single complementary split-ring resonators (CSRRs). We employ a coupled-mode theory framework to guide the waveguide synthesis and gain insight into the underlying physics of periodic grounded uniform and multi-element CSRR metasurfaces, that are the key elements of the corresponding CSRR SIWs. The CSRR SIW parameters are then fine-tuned by a more detailed FEM eigenmode solver. We verify the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW's merit and applicability by fabricating and experimentally characterizing the performance of a CSRR SIW waveguide section and antenna. The uniplanar single-CSRR SIW offers considerably simpler fabrication than both the conventional SIW and previously proposed CSRR SIW variations while maintaining performance. Compared to other SIW variations, the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW has a greater design flexibility, as we can change the number of CSRR rows and also use a non-uniform multi-element CSRR pattern to achieve advanced functionalities. The CSRR-SIW-based periodic leaky-wave antenna (PLWA) has competitive radiation characteristics and simpler fabrication than a corresponding SIW PLWA.

INDEX TERMS Complementary split-ring resonators, periodic leaky-wave antenna, substrate-integrated waveguide, eigenmode analysis, coupled-mode theory.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE SUBSTRATE integrated waveguide (SIW) [1], [2], [3], [4] is a planar transmission line based on metalized via holes and is a dominant choice for microwave and millimeter wave (mmWave) communications. The SIW as well as SIW extensions, such as the air-filled SIW [5], have been used to synthesize various mmWave components over the last twenty years, while it still remains an active area of research, with many SIW components recently proposed [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11]. As communications shift toward higher frequencies, especially in the context of 5G and 6G, the via dimensions are considerably reduced, rendering

drilling holes and injecting metalization a rather complex and costly fabrication technique.

To overcome the fabrication complexity of the metalized via holes, via-less SIW variations have been proposed, which can be realized by PCB fabrication. The corrugated SIW (CSIW) [12] as well as CSIW variations, bent CSIW [13] and the interdigital-capacitor (IDC) CSIW [14], the folded CSIW [15], the twisted CSIW [16] use quarter-wave open-circuit stubs instead of via to form the electric sidewalls. A different solution is the use of metamaterial-inspired SIWs, where each via row is substituted by a metasurface, capable of restricting in-plane propagation. The

metamaterial-inspired SIWs may potentially offer greater design flexibility than the CSIWs, as a different number of rows or even a non-uniform metasurface may be selected depending on the application. Metamaterial-inspired SIWs based on broadside-coupled complementary split-ring resonators (BC-CSRRs), termed the BC-CSRR SIW [17], [18], as well as edge-coupled CSRRs, the EC-CSRR SIW [19], have been introduced in our previous works. Both use two CSRR rows instead of each via row, are planar and have similar losses to the conventional SIW. However, the BC-CSRR SIW requires a precise alignment of the upper and lower CSRRs to avoid higher radiation losses. The EC-CSRR SIW, although uniplanar, has prohibitively fine features, especially for higher frequencies, which have been shown to result in fabrication errors that degrade the EC-CSRR SIW performance. Hence, the need for a uniplanar CSRR-SIW of simpler and stable fabrication emerges. Recently, a uniplanar CSRR SIW based on grounded single CSRRs was introduced [20], [21], which requires a much simpler manufacturing process. However, only a preliminary analysis of a uniform CSRR SIW variation has been carried out. The possibility of tailoring the properties of the CSRR metasurface has not yet been investigated, limiting the functionalities and applicability of the waveguide. Additionally, the performance of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW components has not yet been experimentally validated.

In this work, we explore the full potential and applicability of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW (Fig. 1). By employing a semi-analytical coupled-mode theory (CMT) framework, we analyze CSRR metasurfaces, which are the key elements used to synthesize the CSRR SIW. We consider both a uniform periodic grounded CSRR metasurface as well as a periodic multi-element metasurface supercell of a non-uniform grounded CSRR pattern. The CMT provides insight into the underlying physics of the CSRR metasurfaces as well as guidance to synthesize the corresponding CSRR SIWs. A fine-tuning of the CSRR SIW parameters and a thorough analysis of its properties is carried out by a periodic eigenmode solver. Our analysis is complemented and validated by realistic simulations, component fabrication, and measurements of both the CSRR SIW and a CSRR SIW-based antenna. Measurements and simulations confirm the uniplanar CSRR SIW's potential for synthesizing mmWave components that maintain the conventional SIW's performance while offering considerably simpler fabrication.

II. ANALYSIS OF THE CSRR UNIT CELL AND SUPERCELL

A grounded single CSRR is the key element of the proposed uniplanar CSRR SIW. It acts as a vertical electric dipole, and by virtue of image theory, it is equivalent to a BC-CSRR with both ring gaps placed in the same direction. Both the single CSRR and the corresponding BC-CSRR block in-plane wave propagation near resonance and, consequently, form the guiding channel. The uniplanar CSRR SIW can be synthesized either by a uniform CSRR metasurface or

FIGURE 1. The uniplanar single-CSRR SIW along with its geometric parameters.

FIGURE 2. (a) A uniplanar single-CSRR unit cell with periodic boundary conditions. (b) S-parameters for the grounded uniplanar single-CSRR and the corresponding BC-CSRR of double thickness.

by a periodic multi-element metasurface supercell composed of two or more resonator types. The uniform CSRR metasurface is selected to synthesize a CSRR SIW that achieves transmission in a single band. The supercell can be employed to achieve advanced functionalities, such as dual-band propagation or to produce a bandstop inside the waveguide's passband zone. To demonstrate the bandstop behavior of the grounded single-CSRR metasurfaces and gain further insight into the underlying physics, we examine the properties of their unit cells by a CMT formulation. The CMT results can be used as a starting point for the waveguide synthesis.

A. COUPLED-MODE THEORY FOR A UNIFORM CSRR METASURFACE

The coupled-mode theory is a semi-analytical method that is used to describe the response of a single or multiple resonators, usually coupled to one or more transmission lines [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28]. We consider a uniform periodic CSRR metasurface excited by an incident in-plane wave and analyze its unit cell. The electric field of the incident wave is oriented along the z -axis, considering the axis convention of Fig. 2(a), to resemble the CSRR SIW's TE_{10} mode. The grounded CSRR metasurface unit cell, shown in Fig. 2(a), can be considered a two-port network. The CSRR is not mirror-symmetric along the propagation axis; hence, we consider two different external decay rates $\gamma_{e,in}$ and $\gamma_{e,o}$ to express the coupling between the resonator mode and the input and output ports. The CMT equation is as follows [28]:

$$\frac{d\alpha(t)}{dt} = j\omega_0\alpha(t) - (\gamma_i + \gamma_e)\alpha(t) + d_1s_1^+ + d_2s_2^+, \quad (1)$$

with $\alpha(t)$ being the resonator mode amplitude, $|\alpha(t)|^2$ the energy stored in the resonator, ω_0 the real part of the resonance frequency with losses included, s_1^+ , s_2^+ the amplitudes of an incident wave from each port, γ_i the intrinsic decay rate, accounting for dielectric losses. The external decay rate γ_e can be decomposed into the decay rate into each of the two ports ($\gamma_{e,\text{in}}$, $\gamma_{e,\text{o}}$) and the radiation losses not captured by the two ports $\gamma_{e,r}$, as $\gamma_e = \gamma_{e,\text{in}} + \gamma_{e,\text{o}} + \gamma_{e,r}$. The terms d_1, d_2 are the coupling coefficients between the resonator and the incident wave from each port. The equations that describe the de-excitation of the MSA into the two ports are also required:

$$\begin{bmatrix} s_1^- \\ s_2^- \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{C} \begin{bmatrix} s_1^+ \\ s_2^+ \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} d_1 \\ d_2 \end{bmatrix} \alpha(t), \quad (2)$$

in which s_1^- and s_2^- are the outgoing wave mode amplitudes at each port. The matrix \mathbf{C} describes the direct scattering process and is expressed as $\mathbf{C} = e^{j\theta} \begin{bmatrix} r & jt \\ jt & r \end{bmatrix}$. The parameters r and t are the reflection and transmission coefficients of the direct scattering process and are evaluated by simulating an air-filled parallel-plate transmission line without the CSRR inclusion or the substrate included. The parameter θ corresponds to a phase factor and depends on the position of the reference planes. In [28], it is demonstrated that even for an asymmetric resonator along the propagation axis, the external decay rates $\gamma_{e,\text{in}}$ and $\gamma_{e,\text{o}}$ are equal to each other, provided that the reflection coefficient of the direct scattering process is zero, $r = 0$. In our case, $r = 0$ holds, hence, the coupling coefficients between the resonator mode and each port have amplitudes equal to $|d_1| = |d_2| = \sqrt{2/\gamma_{e,\text{in}}} = \sqrt{2/\gamma_{e,\text{o}}}$.

B. RESONATOR PARAMETERS

The resonator parameters needed for the CMT formulation are obtained by appropriate FEM simulations of a single resonator unit cell. The computational layout of the FEM excitation simulations is included as an inset in Fig. 2(a). The red faces correspond to the input and output ports, with the input port excited by a vertically polarized plane wave. Absorbing boundary conditions (ABCs) are set on the green boundaries on the top and bottom of the unit cell, while perfect magnetic conductor (PMC) boundary conditions are imposed on the remaining boundaries to indirectly force periodicity, accounting for the field symmetries along the x - and y - axes. Operation is targeted around 27 GHz; hence, we start with a set of initial CSRR dimensions $r = 0.865$ mm, $c = 0.3$ mm, $g = 0.3$ mm, with a substrate relative permittivity equal to $\epsilon_r = 2.2 - j0.0022$ and a thickness of $h = 0.8001$ mm. Fig. 2(b) depicts the S-parameters both for the grounded single CSRR and the corresponding BC-CSRR of double thickness. Clearly, they resonate at the same frequency and have an identical response, providing minimum transmission around 27 GHz. Fig. 2(b) confirms the equivalence of the two CSRR unit cells. By observation

FIGURE 3. S-parameters for the grounded uniplanar single-CSRR, calculated by the CMT and FEM.

of Fig. 2(b), we can calculate the resonance's Q-factor, following the Q-factor definition [29]:

$$Q = \frac{f_r}{\Delta f}, \quad (3)$$

where f_r is the resonance frequency and Δf is the full width at half maximum. We perform two excitation simulations; one with dielectric losses included to obtain the total Q-factor and decay rate (Q_{tot} , γ_{tot}) and one with the dielectric losses artificially switched off to determine the external Q-factor and external decay rate (Q_e , γ_e). Each decay rate is related to the corresponding Q-factor as:

$$\gamma_{\text{tot}/e} = \frac{\omega_{\text{tot}/e}}{2Q_{\text{tot},e}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\omega_{\text{tot}/e} = 2\pi f_{r,\text{tot}/e}$ is the angular resonance frequency.

As the external decay rate accounts for both the decay into the ports and the decay into the area above the CSRR, we must determine the contribution of each mechanism. By post-processing the FEM simulation, we calculate the radiated power that does not couple to any of the ports on resonance by appropriate integrations and conclude that the radiated power is negligible, less than 1/10000 of the total power. Hence, the decay rate due to radiation ($\gamma_{e,r}$) is not taken into consideration in the CMT analysis of the grounded CSRR unit cell.

C. CMT RESULTS FOR A UNIFORM CSRR METASURFACE

We calculate the grounded single-CSRR response by the CMT and compare the results to those obtained by the FEM solver. The S-parameter comparison is shown in Fig. 3, and a very good agreement is observed near resonance. Both methods verify that a bandstop appears around 27 GHz.

D. COUPLED-MODE THEORY FOR A PERIODIC MULTI-ELEMENT METASURFACE SUPERCELL

To model a periodic multi-element metasurface supercell consisting of two or more CSRRs, (1) is transformed into [23]:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{A}(t)}{dt} = j\mathbf{\Omega}_0\mathbf{A}(t) - \mathbf{\Gamma}_e\mathbf{A}(t) - \mathbf{\Gamma}_i\mathbf{A}(t) + \mathbf{K}^T \begin{bmatrix} s_1^+ \\ s_2^+ \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

with $\mathbf{A}(t) = [\alpha_1(t), \alpha_2(t), \dots, \alpha_N(t)]^T$ the resonator mode amplitude vector, $\mathbf{\Omega}_0 = \text{diag}(\omega_{t,1}, \omega_{t,2}, \dots, \omega_{t,N})$ the vector of the real part of the resonance frequencies, $\mathbf{\Gamma}_i = \text{diag}(\gamma_{i,1}, \gamma_{i,2}, \dots, \gamma_{i,N})$ the intrinsic decay rate vector,

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & \cdots & d_{1N} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} & \cdots & d_{2N} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

the vector of the coupling coefficient between each resonator and each port. The vector of external decay rates is written as:

$$\mathbf{\Gamma}_e = \begin{bmatrix} \gamma_{e,1} & \kappa_{12} & \cdots & \kappa_{1N} \\ \kappa_{21} & \gamma_{e,2} & \cdots & \kappa_{2N} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \kappa_{N1} & \kappa_{N2} & \cdots & \gamma_{e,N} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

with $\gamma_{e,i}$ the external decay rate of each resonance and κ_{ij} the coupling coefficients between two resonators. As in Section II-A, we neglect the radiation losses as they are negligible. We change (2) to take into account all resonators.

$$\begin{bmatrix} s_1^- \\ s_2^- \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{C} \begin{bmatrix} s_1^+ \\ s_2^+ \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{A}(t). \quad (8)$$

By energy conservation, time-reversal symmetry, and reciprocity, the following conditions apply [23], strictly valid for $\mathbf{\Gamma}_i = 0$.

$$\mathbf{D}^\dagger \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{\Gamma}_e^\dagger + \mathbf{\Gamma}_e, \quad (9a)$$

$$\mathbf{C} \mathbf{D}^* = -\mathbf{D}, \quad (9b)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{D}, \quad (9c)$$

where \dagger denotes the conjugate transpose of the matrix. We note that the condition (9a) can be transformed into the simpler form of $\mathbf{D}^\dagger \mathbf{D} = 2\mathbf{\Gamma}_e$ [23], in case $\mathbf{\Gamma}_e$ is Hermitian, as for instance when the off-diagonal terms accommodate only far-field coupling effects.

We will apply the CMT to a periodic multi-element metasurface supercell of size 2×1 consisting of two CSRRs, one with a ring width of $c_1 = 0.2$ mm and the other with $c_2 = 0.4$ mm, shown in Fig. 4(a). By using (9b) with $r = 0$ and $t = 1$ as in Section II-A, we derive that $|d_{11}| = |d_{21}|$ and $|d_{12}| = |d_{22}|$ for the magnitudes, and $\phi_{11} = -\phi_{21} + \theta + \pi/2 \pm \pi$ and $\phi_{12} = -\phi_{22} + \theta + \pi/2 \pm \pi$ for the phases of the coupling coefficients d_{ij} .

Regarding the coupling coefficients between resonators κ_{ij} , in the more general case, they include both the far-field coupling and near-field coupling [27]. The far-field coupling can be approximated by considering only the single-resonator parameters [30]. Simulations of a pair of resonators are also needed to estimate the near-field coupling, either by analytical expressions involving the complex coupled-resonator frequencies for single-port metasurfaces [27] or fitting the CMT curve to full-wave spectral simulations [25]. In the considered example, we will estimate the metasurface response by taking only the far-field coupling into account, with the coupling coefficients assuming real values, for

FIGURE 4. (a) A 2×1 periodic multi-element supercell with $c_1 = 0.2$ mm and $c_2 = 0.4$ mm (b) S-parameters vs. frequency (GHz) for the supercell of (a), calculated by the CMT and FEM.

a faster yet more approximate estimation. We use the expression $\mathbf{D}^\dagger \mathbf{D} = 2\mathbf{\Gamma}_e$ instead of (9a) and derive the following expressions for the diagonal terms:

$$|d_{11}| = |d_{21}| = \sqrt{\gamma_{e,1}}, \quad (10a)$$

$$|d_{12}| = |d_{22}| = \sqrt{\gamma_{e,2}}. \quad (10b)$$

Hence, even though the resonators are asymmetric with respect to the propagation axis, in this case, where $r = 0$, each mode couples into the two ports with the same amplitude of the coupling coefficient d_{ij} .

By substituting (10) and the relations between the phases of the port coupling-coefficients d_{ij} mentioned above, we derive the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{12} = \kappa_{21} &= \sqrt{\gamma_{e,1}} \sqrt{\gamma_{e,2}} \cos(\phi_{11} - \phi_{12}) \\ &= \sqrt{\gamma_{e,1}} \sqrt{\gamma_{e,2}} \cos(\phi_{22} - \phi_{21}). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

By observing the electric field distribution of each mode at its resonance frequency, it appears that both resonators have close to even modes. Hence, we approximately use the expressions for the case where the two resonances have the same symmetry in [23]. The resonator parameters of each CSRR are calculated following the process described in Section II-B. For the supercell configuration, the FEM simulations of each CSRR are conducted using a computational domain of the supercell with size 2×1 CSRRs.

E. CMT RESULTS FOR A PERIODIC MULTI-ELEMENT CSRR METASURFACE

We apply the CMT formulation to the 2×1 metasurface supercell and compare the calculated S-parameters to those obtained by the FEM solver in Fig. 4(b). The CMT captures both resonances around 25.3 GHz and 29.95 GHz with satisfactory accuracy. A bandstop is located around 27.4 GHz. The effect of the near-field coupling, which is not considered in this case, appears to have a relatively small effect on the metasurface response. By varying the CSRR width c , the radius r , or the gap g of the CSRRs, the bandstop can appear at a different frequency. These results will be used as a starting point for the more detailed FEM-based periodic eigenmode analysis of the waveguide supercell in the upcoming section.

III. DISPERSION ANALYSIS OF THE CSRR SIW

We synthesize the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW for operation around the 27.5 GHz band. We vary the CSRR parameters and aim at obtaining lower leakage losses in the range [26.5, 28.5] GHz. The design parameters, for which leakage losses are lower than 4% of the total losses in the [26.5, 28.5] GHz range, are summarized in Table 1. We analyze the waveguide's propagation characteristics by a periodic eigenmode solver [31]. The operating angular frequency ω is considered known, whereas we seek the complex propagation constant $k = \beta - j\alpha$; the analysis is implemented within the weak form module of COMSOL Multiphysics®. According to the Bloch-Floquet theorem [32], the electric field (\mathbf{E}) may be decomposed into the periodic envelope ($\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$) and a phase term as follows:

$$\mathbf{E} = \tilde{\mathbf{E}} e^{-jk\hat{\mathbf{k}}\cdot\mathbf{r}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{k}}$ denotes the propagation direction, i.e., $\hat{\mathbf{k}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$, following the axis convention of Fig. 1. By applying this transformation to the curl-curl Helmholtz equation in terms of the electric field and weighting with appropriate testing functions, the Galerkin formulation is derived in terms of the electric field envelope $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$. The Floquet periodic boundary conditions are easily implemented as simpler continuity boundary conditions for the field envelope and imposed along the propagation axis x .

The dominant propagating mode of the single-CSRR SIW is the TE_{10} mode, with the electric field norm at mid-substrate shown in Fig. 5(b). We note that the single-CSRR SIW's guiding mechanism significantly differs from that of electromagnetic bandgap (EBG) waveguides [33], [34], [35], which support a quasi-TEM mode instead. We provide the dispersion diagrams of the single-CSRR SIW's supported modes, i.e., the dominant TE_{10} and the attenuated TE_{20} modes, to highlight the waveguide's guiding mechanism. The attenuation and propagation constant of both modes are shown in Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(d). Both dielectric and leakage losses are included in the simulations, with $\epsilon_r = 2.2 - j0.0022$. We observe that the TE_{10} mode moves out of its cut-off region for frequencies close to 24 GHz. The single-CSRR SIW's guiding mechanism depends on the CSRR resonance. The CSRRs act as virtual electric walls, prohibiting in-plane propagation in the vicinity of the CSRR resonance. Therefore, lower leakage loss is achieved around the CSRR resonance, specifically in the [26.5, 28.5] GHz range. We will mainly focus on this lower-loss range. The TE_{20} mode (Fig. 5(c)) has more than an order of magnitude higher losses than the TE_{10} , and thus TE_{10} is dominant. The propagation constant of an SIW with a width $w = 6.5$ mm, metallic via diameter $d = 0.775$ mm and metallic via period $s = 1.525$ mm is also shown in Fig. 5(d). We observe that the propagation constant of the single-CSRR SIW is higher than that of the conventional SIW.

Varying the number of CSRR rows can provide design flexibility by opting for greater bandwidth and lower leakage losses or smaller dimensions instead. We examine the effect

FIGURE 5. (a) The attenuation constant of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW's TE_{10} and TE_{20} modes, (b) the dominant TE_{10} electric field norm, (c) the attenuated TE_{20} electric field norm, and (d) the propagation constant of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW's TE_{10} and TE_{20} modes.

TABLE 1. Uniplanar single-CSRR SIW dimensions.

r (mm)	c (mm)	g (mm)	h (mm)	w (mm)	Period (mm)	ϵ_r
0.89	0.3	0.3	0.8001	6.5	1.98	2.2

FIGURE 6. Attenuation constant (Np/m) vs. frequency (GHz) considering one, two, and three rows of grounded uniplanar CSRRs.

of changing the number of CSRR rows in Fig. 6 by considering only leakage losses and by simulating the CSRR SIW unit cell in the low-loss [26.5, 28.5] GHz range. We use $r = 0.87$ mm for the case of one row so that the lower leakage losses are obtained within the [26.5, 28.5] GHz range. We observe that by increasing the number of rows, lower leakage losses and greater bandwidth are attained. However, the CSRR SIW dimensions also increase. Hence, the double-row configuration is selected as a reasonable trade-off. The offered design flexibility is a distinguishable property of metasurface-based SIWs.

Apart from varying the number of CSRR rows, we can also form a non-uniform periodic multi-element CSRR pattern comprised of two or more resonator types to achieve advanced functionalities using a single component. We

FIGURE 7. Attenuation constant (Np/m) vs. frequency (GHz) for the multi-element uniplanar CSRR SIW (inset), with (i) $c_1 = 0.2$ mm and $c_2 = 0.4$ mm and (ii) $c_1 = 0.2$ mm and $c_2 = 0.5$ mm, using 4 CSRR rows.

synthesize a supercell comprised of two resonator types by using the analysis of Section II to determine initial geometric parameters that produce a bandstop around the desired frequency. The eigenmode analysis can then be used to fine-tune the design parameters and obtain the dispersion diagram of the synthesized supercell, with leakage and dielectric losses included in the simulations. We provide two indicative examples of a supercell with CSRR width values (i) $c_1 = 0.2$ mm and $c_2 = 0.4$ mm for the first and (ii) $c_1 = 0.2$ mm and $c_2 = 0.5$ mm for the second example. The non-uniform CSRR SIW is shown as an inset in Fig. 7, with four CSRR rows, used to confine propagation. A fifth row may be added depending on the application. For the first case, a narrow bandstop region appears around 27.5 GHz within the waveguide's operating frequency range, which is satisfactorily close to the estimation provided by the CMT analysis. Two bandpass regions are formed around 26.5 GHz and 29.5 GHz. We also calculate the attenuation constant for the second example. As the resonances of the individual resonators are located further apart in this case, the attenuation constant is higher in the range [24.8, 28.7] GHz, thus forming a more effective bandstop. The first bandpass region is between 22.85 GHz and 24.55 GHz, whereas the second is between 29 GHz and 32.2 GHz. By calculating the attenuation constant of two different examples, we demonstrate the potential tunability of the multi-element CSRR SIW. We note that although the potential of synthesizing multi-element CSRR patterns applies to all CSRR SIWs, it is demonstrated here for the first time.

We compare the total losses of the uniplanar CSRR SIW, also accounting for copper's conductor losses, to those of the previous CSRR SIW variations and the conventional SIW (Fig. 8). Conductor losses are introduced by imposing impedance boundary conditions (IBC) on the CSRR SIW's metal surfaces. Copper has a conductivity of approximately $\sigma_c = 5.88 \times 10^7$ S/m and a thickness of $t_c = 17$ μ m. The skin depth $\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\omega\mu\sigma_c}}$ is considerably smaller than copper's thickness for the considered frequencies $f = [25,$

FIGURE 8. Attenuation constant (Np/m) vs. frequency (GHz) for the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW, EC-CSRR SIW, BC-CSRR SIW, and conventional SIW.

30] GHz, hence the IBC provides a valid approximation to modeling copper's finite conductivity [36]. The waveguide width w and substrate properties (h , ϵ_r) of Table 1 are chosen in all cases. The BC-CSRR SIW has dimensions as in [17], and the EC-CSRR SIW as in [19]. The conventional SIW has a metallic via diameter of $d = 0.775$ mm, and a metallic via spacing $s = 1.525$ mm, in accordance with the dimensions in [4] for a similar substrate. We note that the design guidelines for low SIW radiation losses $s/d < 2$ and $d/w < 1.5$ are satisfied [2]. The uniplanar single-CSRR SIW has similar losses to the conventional SIW and other CSRR SIW variations within the [26.5, 28.5] GHz range. Since the conventional SIW is a well-established mmWave transmission line, we conclude that the uniplanar CSRR SIW is also suitable for mmWave applications, as it has similar losses to the conventional SIW and simpler fabrication. Obviously, the operating bandwidth of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW will be somewhat narrower than the conventional SIW, as it depends on the CSRR's resonance. Nevertheless, the attained bandwidth is deemed sufficient for numerous mmWave applications, as will also be shown in the upcoming sections, accompanied by fabrication simplicity.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION OF THE UNIPLANAR SINGLE-CSRR SIW

The properties of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW are verified by simulations and measurements of a waveguide section. For this purpose, we add 50 Ω microstrip lines and appropriate transitions to both CSRR SIW ends. The microstrip-line width is $w_m = 2.485$ mm, the tapered section length is $l_t = 6.2832$ mm, the largest tapered section width is $w' = 4.3$ mm, and the total waveguide length is $L_t = 8.756$ cm. Additional single-SRRs are also added to both waveguide ends to avoid extra leakage. We consider a loss tangent of $\tan\delta=0.001$ and apply perfect electric conductor boundary conditions to metal surfaces. The simulated S-parameters of the microstrip-fed single-CSRR SIW are shown in Fig. 9, considering two and three rows of CSRRs to confine propagation. We observe that the dominant TE_{10} 's cut-off frequency is around 24 GHz, which verifies the eigenmode analysis results. Since the single-CSRR SIW is excited by a microstrip line at the center of the waveguide, the TE_{10} is naturally excited. To excite

the TE_{20} mode, a different feeding mechanism would be required that concentrates the maximum electric field values off-center. Additionally, although the TE_{20} mode is supported above approximately 26.5 GHz, it has a considerably higher attenuation constant (as shown in Fig. 5(a)), and hence it cannot propagate. We show the electric field norm at mid-substrate at 27.5 GHz in the inset of Fig. 9, verifying that indeed the TE_{10} is the propagating mode. We also note that the single-CSRR SIW operates in the vicinity of the CSRR resonance. For higher frequencies and as we move further away from the CSRR resonance, leakage losses become higher, and consequently, the transmission coefficient starts to decrease. Adding a third CSRR row can slightly enhance the CSRR SIW's operational bandwidth.

To assess the uniplanar CSRR SIW losses, we simulate the microstrip-fed uniplanar single-CSRR SIW both by using a loss tangent of 0.001 and a more realistic value of 0.003 for the substrate and by including conductor losses. Conductor losses are introduced as IBCs, as in the eigenmode analysis simulations. Using IBCs instead of introducing copper as a material of finite conductivity and thickness provides both a valid approximation and a computationally tractable approach, especially in excitation simulations, where numerous degrees of freedom are required. In Fig. 10, we show the S-parameters of the simulated microstrip-fed CSRR SIW section for both loss tangent values. The transmission loss of the case with $\tan\delta=0.001$ is lower than the case of $\tan\delta=0.003$ by about 0.8 dB. We also compare the S-parameters of the microstrip-fed single-CSRR SIW with $\tan\delta=0.001$ to a microstrip-fed conventional SIW of the same length and material properties, with the dimensions used in Section III. Our single-CSRR SIW has a slightly lower transmission loss between 25.3 GHz and 27.9 GHz by about 0.3 dB. The two SIW variations have equal transmission loss between 27.9 GHz and 28.9 GHz. Our single-CSRR SIW achieves transmission losses similar to or lower than the SIW around the CSRR resonance, between 25.3 GHz and 28.9 GHz. We emphasize that our single-CSRR SIW's bandwidth is sufficient for several timely mmWave applications.

The CSRR SIW section is also fabricated and experimentally characterized. The measurements are compared against more realistic simulations, which include the effect of K-connectors and a loss tangent of $\tan\delta=0.003$. The transmission loss increases by adding the K-connectors, and is between 3.6 dB and 4.1 dB in the [26.5, 28.5] GHz range. The higher losses attributed to the K-connectors are common to measurements of all planar transmission lines, hence, we provide validation that the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW can be indeed used in mmWave applications. A satisfactory agreement between measurements and simulations is attained, as shown in Fig. 11. A small mismatch is anticipated between simulations and measurements and may be mainly attributed to the difficulty of achieving the K-connectors' precise positioning. A photograph of the fabricated sample is also included in Fig. 11 as an inset. Measurements

FIGURE 9. Simulated S-parameters of a microstrip-fed uniplanar single-CSRR SIW with 2 and 3 CSRR rows. A loss tangent of $\tan\delta = 0.001$ and PEC boundary conditions are considered. The electric field norm at 27.5 GHz is shown as an inset.

FIGURE 10. Simulated S-parameters of a microstrip-fed uniplanar single-CSRR SIW. A loss tangent of $\tan\delta = 0.001$ and $\tan\delta = 0.003$ is considered. Conductors are modeled as impedance boundary conditions. The S-parameters of a microstrip-fed conventional SIW are also shown.

FIGURE 11. Measured (m) and simulated (s) S-parameters of a uniplanar single-CSRR SIW, with a photograph of the fabricated sample shown as an inset.

provide the necessary verification of our single-CSRR SIW's merit.

V. CSRR SIW PERIODIC LEAKY-WAVE ANTENNA

To highlight the proposed SIW's potential as a valuable candidate for synthesizing functional and easily manufacturable mmWave components, we design a Ka-band periodic leaky-wave antenna (PLWA) based on the proposed transmission line. We show that it achieves similar radiation characteristics to a conventional-SIW-based PLWA, while

also being accompanied by easier fabrication. We choose to design and experimentally characterize a PLWA, as it offers the advantages of higher gain and a beam steering ability over monopole antennas, such as bow-tie antennas [37].

The PLWA is designed in a similar fashion to the ones designed for other SIW variations [13], [18], [19], [38], with twenty-five transverse slots etched on the upper broad wall, with the first five linearly tapered to suppress undesired reflections. We design the PLWA with the CSRR SIW dimension of Table 1, slot length $l_s = 3.2$ mm, slot width $w_s = 0.9$ mm, and slot periodicity $p_s = 5.94$ mm. To compare the radiation characteristics of the PLWA to a similar PLWA based on the conventional SIW, we consider an SIW-based PLWA which uses the same substrate ($\epsilon_r = 2.2(1 - j0.003)$, $h = 0.8001$ mm), slot dimensions and number of slots as the proposed PLWA. The SIW has a via diameter of $d = 0.775$ mm and a period of $s = 1.525$ mm. The slot period of the SIW-based PLWA is slightly greater than that of the CSRR-SIW-based PLWA, $p_s = 6.732$ mm instead of $p_s = 5.94$ mm, to achieve a similar main beam direction for both antennas. The propagation constant of the PLWA's radiating -1 -space-harmonic leaky mode is calculated as $\beta_{-1} = \beta_0 - 2\pi/p_s$, where β_0 is the propagation constant of the transmission line's TE₁₀ mode. The main lobe direction depends on the leaky mode's propagation constant and is calculated as $\sin\theta_{-1} = \beta_{-1}/k_0$. Since the conventional SIW has lower propagation constant (β_0) than the single-CSRR SIW, as shown in Fig. 5(d), we consider a greater slot period, so that the β_{-1} and angle θ_{-1} attain close values. As the SIW PLWA would occupy greater space along the propagation axis, we move all its slots toward the feeding system by 1.35 cm to accommodate them within the same length as the CSRR SIW PLWA. We simulate both the uniplanar CSRR-SIW-based PLWA and the SIW-based PLWA using COMSOL Multiphysics, with K-connectors included in both simulations and PEC boundary conditions imposed on conductor surfaces.

The proposed PLWA is also fabricated with its performance experimentally verified, using 24.7 dBi standard-gain horn antennas. The receiving horn antenna is oriented so that the horn antenna's electric field is oriented along the PLWA's propagation axis. A photograph of the fabricated antenna is shown in Fig. 14. The measured far-field gain radiation pattern is compared against the corresponding simulations in Fig. 13, and a good agreement is observed in all cases. Simulations show that the proposed antenna features a high gain of about 16.5–18 dBi, with the higher sidelobes positioned about 10–12 dB lower than the main lobe. The simulated efficiency of the uniplanar CSRR SIW is compared to that of the conventional SIW in Fig. 12. We consider the radiation efficiency, calculated as $\eta_r = P_{r,\text{tot}}/P_i$, where $P_{r,\text{tot}}$ is the radiated power, calculated by integration of the Poynting vector on all external boundaries of the computational domain, and P_i is the input power inserted into the antenna's K-connector, which is 1 Watt. We also consider the efficiency including the impedance

FIGURE 12. Radiation efficiency and efficiency with impedance mismatch included of the uniplanar CSRR SIW and conventional SIW PLWAs.

mismatch loss $\eta_t = \eta_m \eta_r$, where $\eta_m = 1 - |S_{11}|^2$. We observe that the two PLWAs have similar efficiency values between 25 and 28.5 GHz, whereas the uniplanar CSRR SIW PLWA has higher efficiency values above 28.5 GHz. As expected the efficiency with impedance mismatch loss included is somewhat lower than the radiation efficiency, especially above 29 GHz. The uniplanar single-CSRR SIW PLWA's η_r is between 57–82.4% and η_t between 54–80%, whereas the SIW PLWA has η_r between 36–78% and a η_t between 24–75%. Higher efficiency values can be potentially achieved both for the CSRR SIW and conventional SIW, if a lower loss dielectric substrate is used. Regarding the single-CSRR-SIW PLWA gain, the measured maximum gain is about 2–3 dB lower than the simulated one, probably due to the effect of soldering the connectors, which is a reasonable deviation that may also be observed in conventional SIW PLWAs [39], [40]. The maximum gain is also similar to conventional SIW PLWA, with our uniplanar single-CSRR SIW PLWA achieving slightly higher values by up to 0.5 dB, as shown in Fig. 13. The side lobe level (SLL) has some variation between the two PLWAs. However, the maximum SLL values of the two PLWAs are very close. Specifically, the maximum SLL for the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW- and SIW-PLWA is 10.24 dB and 11 dB at 27 GHz, 10.8 dB and 10.1 dB at 28 GHz, 9.5 dB and 9 dB at 26 GHz. Both simulations and measurements of the single-CSRR-SIW PLWA's reflection coefficient verify that it is lower than -10 dB within a broad frequency range, between 25 and 29.7 GHz (simulation results of Fig. 14). The conventional-SIW PLWA is also broadband. Overall, the single-CSRR-SIW PLWA has competitive radiation characteristics to the conventional-SIW implementation.

VI. COMPARISON TO RELATED WORKS

We summarize the distinguishable characteristics and advantages of the proposed uniplanar single-CSRR SIW, compared to state-of-the-art transmission lines in Table 2: specifically, we consider our previous metamaterial-inspired SIWs, the conventional SIW, as well various CSIW variations. By ranking them by fabrication simplicity, with 1 being the easiest to fabricate, we highlight that our proposed uniplanar single-CSRR SIW offers even simpler fabrication than the previous

FIGURE 13. Measured (m) and simulated (s) radiation pattern - gain (dBi).

FIGURE 14. $|S_{11}|$ (dB) and photograph of the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW PLWA. The simulated $|S_{11}|$ of the conventional SIW is also shown.

CSRR SIWs and the conventional SIW, as it is uniplanar and has fewer fine features than the EC-CSRR SIW. Compared to the CSIWs, which are as easy to fabricate as our single-CSRR SIW, the proposed SIW uses a different mechanism to restrict the propagating wave: a two-dimensional CSRR metasurface instead of corrugated $\lambda_g/4$ stubs. The two-dimensional CSRR metasurface offers the ability of changing the number of CSRR rows, which allows trading smaller occupied space for enhanced bandwidth and lower leakage losses, and vice versa. This aspect has been designated in Table 2 in the column “Vary no. rows”. The 2D CSRR metasurface also allows the forming of a non-uniform multi-element resonator pattern, comprised of CSRRs of different dimensions. A non-uniform single-CSRR SIW, as is the one presented in Fig. 7, offers advanced filtering functionalities, such as dual-band propagation over two well-separated frequency bands, or a bandstop within the waveguide’s operating frequencies in a unified design without separate feeding systems. The concept of using a non-uniform metasurface has not been investigated either for the CSIWs or for other CSRR-SIW variations. The fact that the CSRR SIWs use two-dimensional metasurfaces instead of one-dimensional, offer increased design flexibility when designing non-uniform metasurface patterns, as there are additional resonators to tune. Non-uniformity has been addressed by adding the column “Non unif. MS” to Table 2.

The transmission loss per unit length (dB/(10cm)) has been also included for a more thorough assessment of the SIWs’ performance. We consider a dielectric substrate of $\epsilon_r = 2.2 - j 0.0022$ and thickness $h = 0.8001$ mm for all considered transmission lines and PEC boundary conditions on all metal surfaces. We also set the inner width to $w_i = 4.72$ mm for

TABLE 2. Comparison to state-of-the-art transmission lines, ranked from easiest to fabricate, denoted as 1, to that of more complex fabrication 4.

Ref.	Wave restr. mech.	No. Rows	Intern. width (mm)	Wall width (mm)	λ_g (mm)	Easy to fabr.	Vary no. rows	Non unif. MS	Trans. Loss p.u.l. (dB/10cm)
[1]	via	1	5.725	0.78	9.3	4	no	no	0.48
			4.72		10.8				0.56
[18]	BC-CSRR	2	4.72	3.66	8	3	yes	no	0.52
[19]	EC-CSRR	2	4.72	3.52	8	2	yes	no	0.48
[12]*	$\lambda_g/4$ stubs	1	4.72	2.70	8.1	1	no	no	0.48
[14] ⁺	interdig. capacitor	1	4.72	3.10	8.4	1	no	no	0.476
	$\lambda_g/4$ stubs								
[13]	bent	1	4.72	1.80	8	1	no	no	0.44
	$\lambda_g/4$ stubs								
[16]	twisted	1	4.72	2.20	8.2	1	no	no	0.50
	$\lambda_g/4$ stubs								
This work	2D single CSRR MS	2	4.72	3.86	7.8	1	yes	yes	0.44
		1		1.73	7.9				0.62 ⁺⁺

* As [12] is in the X-band, dimensions are taken from [14]. ⁺ A stub length of 3 mm is used to set the lower loss band around 27.5 GHz.

⁺⁺ It is 0.51 dB/(10 cm) within 1 GHz range.

all transmission lines. The waveguide width w is related to the inner width w_i as $w = w_i + 2r$, for the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW. Although in the previous sections we considered an identical waveguide width w between the CSRR SIWs and conventional SIW, here we choose an identical inner width w_i , as it is a more common parameter in the CSIW-related articles. For the conventional SIW, we also show the transmission loss for the dimensions considered in Sections III-V, with $w = 6.5$ mm and $w_i = 5.725$ mm, which has lower losses than the $w_i = 4.72$ mm case. We calculate the complex propagation constant of the dominant TE_{10} mode by the eigenmode solver, with dielectric losses included, and obtain the average attenuation constant within the [26.5, 28.5] GHz band. The transmission loss per unit length is calculated as $\alpha(\text{dB}/(10\text{cm})) = \alpha(\text{Np}/\text{m}) \cdot 0.8686$. Our single-CSRR SIW has similar or lower losses than all other SIW variations.

We also compare the SIWs in terms of miniaturization. Specifically, we compare the size of the virtual wall (i.e., via/ CSRR metasurface/ corrugated stub), which shows the occupied space in the transverse direction. We observe that the single-CSRR SIW occupies a somewhat greater space than the corrugated SIW variations and the SIW when two CSRR rows are considered. When minimizing the transverse dimension is most important, we can use a single-CSRR SIW with one CSRR row, which occupies a smaller space than all CSIW variations. Of course, we note that the transmission loss p.u.l. is comparable to other SIW variations within a narrower 1 GHz range, which may be sufficient for certain mmWave applications. Apart from the transverse dimensions, we also compare the guided wavelength, which is calculated as $\lambda_g = 2\pi/\beta$, where β is the TE_{10} mode’s propagation constant and is averaged over the [26.5, 28.5] GHz range. Our single-CSRR SIW has the highest propagation constant

and, hence, the smallest guided wavelength. By having the smallest guided wavelength, our single-CSRR SIW can be used to design components with smaller longitudinal dimensions. Therefore, regarding miniaturization, the single-CSRR SIW has greater transverse dimensions but smaller longitudinal dimensions than the other SIW variations.

VII. CONCLUSION

We introduced and fully explored the properties of a uniplanar single-CSRR SIW, which is suitable for realizing easy-to-fabricate mmWave components. The uniplanar single-CSRR SIW offers considerably simpler fabrication than both the conventional SIW and previously proposed CSRR SIW variations while maintaining performance. A coupled-mode theory framework is used to gain physical insight and initial design parameters on the response of grounded single-CSRR and multi-element CSRR metasurfaces that synthesize the corresponding CSRR SIWs. A more thorough analysis and fine-tuning of the uniplanar CSRR SIW is conducted by an eigenmode solver, with emphasis given to the advanced functionalities that can be achieved by tailoring the CSRR metasurface resonators. We demonstrate the uniplanar single-CSRR SIW's merit by fabricating and experimentally characterizing the performance of a CSRR SIW waveguide section and an antenna.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The publication of the article in OA mode was financially supported by HEAL-Link.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Deslandes and K. Wu, "Single-substrate integration technique of planar circuits and waveguide filters," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 593–596, Feb. 2003.
- [2] F. Xu and K. Wu, "Guided-wave and leakage characteristics of substrate integrated waveguide," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 66–72, Jan. 2005.
- [3] D. Deslandes and K. Wu, "Accurate modeling, wave mechanisms, and design considerations of a substrate integrated waveguide," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 54, no. 6, pp. 2516–2526, Jun. 2006.
- [4] M. Bozzi, L. Perregrini, and K. Wu, "Modeling of conductor, dielectric, and radiation losses in substrate integrated waveguide by the boundary integral-resonant mode expansion method," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 56, no. 12, pp. 3153–3161, Dec. 2008.
- [5] F. Parment, A. Ghiotto, T. P. Vuong, J. M. Duchamp, and K. Wu, "Air-filled substrate integrated waveguide for low-loss and high power-handling millimeter-wave substrate integrated circuits," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 1228–1238, Apr. 2015.
- [6] P. Chu et al., "Substrate integrated waveguide filter with flexible mixed coupling," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 71, no. 9, pp. 4003–4011, Sep. 2023.
- [7] K. Zhou and K. Wu, "Substrate integrated waveguide multiband bandpass filters and multiplexers: Current status and future outlook," *IEEE J. Microw.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 466–483, Jan. 2023.
- [8] F. Zhu, Q. Luo, Z. Liao, X. Dai, and K. Wu, "Compact dual-mode bandpass filters based on half-mode substrate-integrated waveguide cavities," *IEEE Microw. Wireless Compon. Lett.*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 441–444, May 2021.
- [9] H.-T. Hu and C. Chan, "Substrate-integrated-waveguide-fed wideband filtering antenna for millimeter-wave applications," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 8125–8135, Dec. 2021.
- [10] L. Silvestri, A. Ghiotto, C. Tomassoni, M. Bozzi, and L. Perregrini, "Partially air-filled substrate integrated waveguide filters with full control of transmission zeros," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 67, no. 9, pp. 3673–3682, Sep. 2019.
- [11] G. Zhang et al., "Design of wide-stopband and dual-band filtering crossovers based on mixed substrate integrated waveguide cavities," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 71, no. 12, pp. 5346–5357, Dec. 2023.
- [12] K. Eccleston, "Mode analysis of the corrugated substrate integrated waveguide," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 60, no. 10, pp. 3004–3012, Oct. 2012.
- [13] Y. Lin, Y. Zhang, H. Liu, Y. Zhang, E. Forsberg, and S. He, "A simple high-gain millimeter-wave leaky-wave slot antenna based on a bent corrugated SIW," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 91999–92006, 2020.
- [14] A. Bansal, C. J. Panagamuwa, and W. G. Whittow, "Millimeter-wave beam steerable slot array antenna using an inter-digitated capacitor based corrugated SIW," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, no. 12, pp. 11761–11770, Dec. 2022.
- [15] D. Cho and H.-Y. Lee, "Folded corrugated SIW (FCSIW) slot antenna for backlobe suppression," *IEEE Antennas Propag. Lett.*, vol. 12, pp. 1276–1279, 2013.
- [16] U. Pandey, P. Singh, N. Gupta, R. Singh, and A. Bansal, "Wideband leaky-wave antenna with dumbbell-shaped slots on substrate integrated waveguides with twisted corrugations," *Electron. Lett.*, vol. 59, no. 20, pp. 1–3, 2023.
- [17] M. Nitas, M.-T. Passia, and T. Yioultsis, "Analysis and design of a CSRR-based fully planar substrate-integrated waveguide for millimeter-wave circuits and antennas," in *Proc. 11th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Paris, France, 2017, pp. 3501–3505.
- [18] M. Nitas, M.-T. Passia, and T. Yioultsis, "Fully planar slow-wave substrate integrated waveguide based on broadside-coupled complementary split ring resonators for mmWave and 5G components," *IET Microw. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 14, no. 10, pp. 1096–1107, 2020.
- [19] M.-T. Passia and T. Yioultsis, "A uniplanar substrate integrated waveguide based on edge-coupled complementary split-ring resonators for millimeter-wave components," in *Proc. 15th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Dusseldorf, Germany, 2021, pp. 1–5.
- [20] M.-T. Passia and T. Yioultsis, "New uniplanar and broadside-coupled CSRR substrate integrated waveguides for mmWave components," in *Proc. 16th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Madrid, Spain, 2022, pp. 1–5.
- [21] M.-T. Passia and T. Yioultsis, "A uniplanar low-sidelobe periodic leaky-wave antenna based on a metamaterial-inspired substrate integrated waveguide," in *Proc. 17th Eur. Conf. Antennas Propag. (EuCAP)*, Florence, Italy, 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [22] S. Fan, W. Suh, and J. D. Joannopoulos, "Temporal coupled-mode theory for the Fano resonance in optical resonators," *J. Opt. Soc. Amer. A, Opt. Image Sci.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 569–572, 2003.
- [23] W. Suh, Z. Wang, and S. Fan, "Temporal coupled-mode theory and the presence of non-orthogonal modes in lossless multimode cavities," *IEEE J. Quantum. Electron.*, vol. 40, no. 10, pp. 1511–1518, Oct. 2004.
- [24] T. Christopoulos, O. Tsilipakos, N. Grivas, and E. Kriezis, "Coupled-mode-theory framework for nonlinear resonators comprising graphene," *Phys. Rev. E, Stat. Phys. Plasmas Fluids Relat. Interdiscip. Top.*, vol. 94, 2016, Art. no. 62219.
- [25] R. Audhkhasi, B. Zhao, S. Fan, Z. Yu, and M. L. Povinelli, "Spectral emissivity modeling in multi-resonant systems using coupled-mode theory," *Opt. Exp.*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 9463–9472, 2022.
- [26] X. Huang, C. Yeung, and A. P. Raman, "Temporal coupled-mode theory for thermal emission from multiple arbitrarily coupled resonators," *Phys. Rev. Appl.*, vol. 19, Mar. 2023, Art. no. 34037.
- [27] M.-T. Passia, T. Yioultsis, and E. Kriezis, "A coupled-mode-theory formulation for periodic multi-element metasurfaces in the presence of radiation losses," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 135, Jan. 2024, Art. no. 23102.
- [28] K. Wang, Z. Yu, S. Sandhu, and S. Fan, "Fundamental bounds on decay rates in asymmetric single-mode optical resonators," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 38, no. 2, pp. 2265–2273, 2013.
- [29] T. Christopoulos, O. Tsilipakos, G. Sinatkas, and E. Kriezis, "On the calculation of the quality factor in contemporary photonic resonant structures," *Opt. Exp.*, vol. 27, no. 10, pp. 14505–14522, 2019.

- [30] M. Zhou et al., "Inverse design of metasurfaces based on coupled-mode theory and adjoint optimization," *ACS Photon.*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 2265–2273, 2021.
- [31] C. Fietz, Y. Urzhumov, and G. Shvets, "Complex k band diagrams of 3D metamaterial/photonic crystals," *Opt. Exp.*, vol. 19, no. 20, pp. 19027–19041, 2011.
- [32] A. Yariv and P. Yeh, *Optical Waves in Crystals*. New York, NY, USA: Wiley, 1984.
- [33] E. Rajo-Inglesias and P.-S. Kildal, "Numerical studies of bandwidth of parallel-plate cut-off realised by a bed of nails, corrugations and mushroom-type electromagnetic bandgap for use in gap waveguides," *IET Microw. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 282–289, 2011.
- [34] N. Bayat-Makou and A. A. Kishk, "Realistic air-filled tem printed parallel-plate waveguide based on ridge gap waveguide," *IEEE Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 66, no. 5, pp. 2128–2140, May 2018.
- [35] S. Peng, Y. Pu, Z. Wu, X. Chen, and Y. Luo, "Embedded bed of nails with robustness suitable for broadband gap waveguide technology," *IEEE Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 5317–5326, Dec. 2021.
- [36] S. Yuferev and N. Ida, *Surface Impedance Boundary Conditions: A Comprehensive Approach*. Boca Raton, FL, USA: Taylor & Francis Group/CRC Press, 2010.
- [37] C. Feng, T. Shi, and L. Wang, "Novel broadband bow-tie antenna based on complementary split-ring resonators enhanced substrate-integrated waveguide," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 12397–12404, 2019.
- [38] J. Liu, D. R. Jackson, and Y. Long, "Substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) leaky-wave antenna with transverse slots," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 20–29, Jan. 2012.
- [39] J. Liu and J. Liang, "Gain enhancement of transversely slotted substrate integrated waveguide leaky-wave antennas based on higher modes," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 69, no. 8, pp. 4423–4438, Aug. 2021.
- [40] Y. Geng, J. Wang, Z. Li, Y. Li, M. Chen, and Z. Zhang, "Dual-beam and tri-band SIW leaky-wave antenna with wide beam scanning range including broadside direction," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 176361–176368, 2019.

MARIA-THALEIA PASSIA received the Diploma and Ph.D. degrees in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece, in 2015 and 2020, respectively. She is currently a MSCA Global Postdoctoral Fellow with Duke University, USA. Her research interests include the analysis and design of metamaterial devices for microwave and millimeter-wave applications, as well as the development of semi-analytical formulations for the fast synthesis of complex metasurface structures.

TRAIANOS V. YIOULTSIS (Member, IEEE) received the Diploma degree in electrical engineering and Ph.D. degree in electrical and computer engineering from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH), Thessaloniki, Greece, in 1992 and 1998, respectively, where he was a Research and Teaching Assistant with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering from 1993 to 1998. From 2001 to 2002 he was a Postdoctoral Research Associate with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL, USA. Since 2002, he has been with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, AUTH, where he is currently a Professor. His current interests include the analysis and design of microwave/photonic circuits and antennas with fast computational and optimization techniques and the modeling of complex wave propagation problems.